

EQUIVALENCE PROBLEMS IN TRANSLATION

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Abstract: In this article, topics related to the issue of equivalence in translation studies, equivalence the question of the role of levels and the method of application is relevant problems are analyzed. The purpose of this work the problem raised in the issue of equivalence identification, significance of equivalence levels, original and translated text is to compare the semantic proximity of equivalence between them.

Key words: equivalence, translation, levels, text, translation problems, adequacy, reference.

Despite the existence of the highly sophisticated modern means of international communication that have reduced the distances between individuals and communities and despite the wide use of the English language for communication among the nations of the globe, translation is still an indispensable means, not only of communication among nations, but also for facilitating access to science and knowledge worldwide.

The translated text is equal to the original text and has the same image of integrity should wake up. Accordingly, one of the tasks of translation is the translation of the original text it is equal to the possibility of taking a full communicative place and the original student provide a balanced balance of artistic pleasure, content and structure is to achieve. Such a balance should cover all aspects of translation.

Giving on the issue of equivalence of linguists and translators opinions different . According to some translators, the language being translated giving the main content while strictly following the norm is an equivalent translation and it is noted that this is an acceptable situation. "Equivalent" equality in general and, firstly, if equivalence implies no similarity at all, the second is an equivalent substitution.

It is important to recognize the levels of equivalence in translation. This has been interpreted differently by linguists and translators. Translation as a special type of interlingual communication focuses on two languages is a creative process that requires focusing on the meaning aspect of the system. Because the basis of completeness of information is the spiritual harmony of the texts of different languages is enough. One of the tasks of the goal of communication is to fully ensure the aspects of the semantic alternative of any image means in translation.

Usually, in literary translation, phraseological expressions from one language into another language translating using equivalents is the most efficient way to create an adequate translation is considered Because equivalents are figurative in addition to the meanings of expressions the bases are also similar to each other. This is their stylistic function- ensures that one is more suitable. That is why professional translators they try to use this method more during their work. However

phrases in the original target language even when translated using equivalents without deep understanding of their meanings and stylistic functions use may result in failure of adequacy. We give following one based on equivalent English and Uzbek phraseological expressions:

«Fish begins to stink at the head»//»Baliq boshidan sasiydi»

«The dog bark, but the caravan goes on»//»It hurar - karvon o'tar»

«Cut your coat according your cloth»//»Ko'rpangga qarab oyoq uzat» [1]

Thus, we see that translation is an operation or process, but at the same time, it is a product: It is an abstract concept consisting of the process and the product. This means that translation is a process of transference operating among languages, that is, it is an interpretation of the verbal symbols in one language via the symbols of other languages. It is also an intra-language process: the translator often resorts to interpreting the source text by using the tools of the source language itself (vocabulary items and structure) when facing some difficulty in absorbing the message. He or she may look for the synonyms of a vocabulary item, paraphrase a text, or simplify it in order to grasp the meaning and then render it in a proper form in the target language [2].

Translation must be reliable and valid: The meaning should not be changed regardless of the number of times it has been translated and should be valid as long as the translator translates what he is supposed to translate. In other words, he should not add or delete anything of the message in target language. Thus translation consists of several diverse dimensions: It can refer to the process, the product, or the abstract concept of translation. The process focuses on what a translator does in turning the source text (ST) into a target text (TT) in another language. The sense of product centers on the outcome of the process. The sense of abstract concept of the general phenomenon compromises the subject field. In fact, translation is a process and a product: In the process, the translator renders the message in the target language. The outcome message should be complete, clear, and accurate fulfilling the objective of the source text. The translator should be concerned about the effect of the outcome translation on the receiver of the translation. So translation can be a process of transferring the message of the source text into a target text. The outcome should be an acceptable translation as long as it carries with it all the meanings and objectives of the source text.

Equivalence is undoubtedly one of the most challenging and contentious areas in the field of translation theory. The term has been triggering heated debates within the field of translation studies but these debates are totally overlooked in practice. Translators rarely resort to such theoretical work when they translate. Perhaps this claim needs verification. Discussions of the concept of equivalence in translation have triggered further studies and explanations of the term by contemporary theorists but despite this elaboration, it has been difficult to define equivalence. As a result, it has not been feasible to agree on a universal approach to the concept due to a great gap between theory and practice in translation.

Components present in an expression in one language are formal in an expression in the second language absent, but those absent components are also present when pronouncing the phrase is caught. As can be seen in the given examples, these expressions are Uzbek variants It is shorter than the English version, that is, it is available in the Uzbek version. Some of the

components that were there have been dropped. But also phrases in Uzbek language pronunciation refers to those omitted components.

On the contrary, phraseological expressions in one language are alternatives to another language translation using also results in the translation being the same as the original. The difficulty with translation is that it is in the translation language to translate the phrase it is necessary to be able to choose the most suitable synonymic expressions. For instance:

«Every dog is lion at home»// har kim o'z uyida bek» [2].

The phraseological equivalents of two languages that are materially similar are semantic and stylistic in terms of tasks, in most cases they are compatible with each other, because such sometimes units are based on concepts based on the same life experience. These same expressions can easily replace each other in translation. The original is the interaction between the author of the text and the recipient of the translation of the text and the translator the influence of translation conditions and the recipient's demand, the translator's communicative effect the skill of understanding delivery, the actual or assumed recipient of his oratory work changes according to their ideas about it and determines the compatibility in the translation.

Adequate interpretation of phrases in translation is a very difficult part of translation practice and at the same time, it is a very responsible matter. Because they are speech more than a simple, neutral statement of an idea as an artistic and visual means participates in the expression of various methodological tasks. From the research of many researchers, it became clear that phrases are the language as a unified lexical unit, it is grammatical, semantic, functional, even sociological. It is shown that it is possible to learn. In addition, many expressions are national has a feature that causes difficulties for translators. Every language is a phrase social events belonging to the life of the people, moral and spiritual and cultural standards, mental states, religious imagination, national traditions and customs will be reflected.

"In order to achieve an authentic translation, the original is artistic - aesthetic value, two languages lexical compatibility of linguistic means and belonging to the original factors related to the material, spiritual, political and economic life of the people should be fully reflected in the translation". That's all there are masterpieces of literary translation increases. So, to revive the practice of translation, modernize the theory of translation we are all responsible for raising the level of world science.

The question raised in the study can be revisited here. Is translation really a process of substituting a text in one language for a text in another? The review of related literature and the examples provided in the study and other studies show that translation is not a mere substitution of texts among languages. The translator must be aware of the objectives and the all the meanings conveyed in the source text. If one shade of meaning is lost in translation, then the text rendered in the target language is a failure. Producing non-equivalents in translation is inappropriate and distorts or blurs the meaning. Translation is the most difficult task to do for translation should not be a poor substitute for the original. Duff says “Translation does have a bad reputation with general public”. Torture and translation are, in fact, amongst the few fates that can be worse than death. Strictly speaking, translation is a subtle form of torture [3].

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